

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF USING HISTORICAL SOURCES IN MUSIC CULTURE LESSONS IN FORMING STUDENTS' VIEWS OF THE WORLD

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Abstract: In this article, the role and importance of historical-scientific-heritage sources in shaping the world view and thinking skills of students in music culture lessons is highlighted.

Key words: Scientific-theoretical heritage, musicology, education, teacher and student, creative thinking.

It is known that the attitude to the national spirituality, which expresses the spirit, worldview and lifestyle of the people, its development based on the requirements of the time, and the issue of changing the worldview and thinking of the young generation in accordance with the development of the time, requires deep and careful consideration in all aspects. In this regard, first of all, it is necessary to properly explain the concepts of national spirituality, national culture, national ideology, and national heritage to the young generation, to make them deeply understand the essence and content of these concepts, and to adhere to these concepts throughout their lives. It is necessary to teach them to understand that it is a human virtue to convey concepts to the next generations.

It is known that the history of the emergence and development of the views and teachings of our ancestors on spirituality and enlightenment spans several thousand years. That is why it is necessary to study the cultural heritage and educational and spiritual values in a wide and comprehensive way, as stated by the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A. Karimov, one of the most important tasks of today is to restore the spiritual and moral values of our people, our great ancestors, It consists of turning the heritage of poets and scientists into the property of the people, revealing the stages and features of the formation of the deep historical roots of the people's own culture and spirituality. This, in turn, serves to develop national consciousness, pride, respect for our history, the service of past generations, people's work, love for the motherland, and national pride.

Historical experiences show that the main goal of any country's educational system, including music, is to instill in young people the material and spiritual wealth and values inherited from their ancestors, combined with modern knowledge. Analyzing the historical path taken to solve this complex and urgent task, identifying its positive and negative aspects, creating a system of effective

new pedagogical tools aimed at educating, especially the spiritual qualities of students, based on this necessity is put on the agenda.

Collecting information about the pedagogical importance, spiritual heritage, place of pedagogical views of historical sources, which are not included in the history of music, educational and educational value, and the experiences of representatives of our nation in the field of education and education, and including them in the educational process;

To analyze the requirements for the knowledge, skills and qualifications that must be mastered in the history of music from the point of view of the needs of the time and to use them in practice;

To acquaint the students with the history of the nation, to create in them knowledge about the path of development of the nation, to determine the confidence in the future based on the national history;

To make students understand that fighting for the freedom of the nation, the independence, development and prospects of the Motherland is a family and human civic duty, to arouse the desire to work tirelessly for the development of society and the power of the state;

To acquaint students with the lifestyle of the nation, the approach to existence, the content of social relations, the characteristics of the national character, and to educate them in the qualities characteristic of the national mentality.

To provide students with information about the factors that are important for the life, past, and future of the nation, to create an opportunity for them to fully understand the characteristics of the national mentality, to inculcate in students national traditions, rituals and traditions. education of practical action skills in order to be continued by them, to enrich them in terms of content; Formation of scientific knowledge in students about the historical roots of folk music, its sources and the development of musical art in different eras, their role in personal development in the period of scientific and technical development, as well as the means of using folklore in the educational process. ; Historical sites, trips to historical monuments; Organization of excursions to historical museums and museums of art history and home museums of our nation's scholars; Using the wealth of scientific libraries that serve to collect, preserve and convey the history of our great generations to the people, holding meetings with scientists studying our spiritual, cultural and scientific heritage.

In the course of the lesson, it is not good to explain these rules to the students by way of description and limiting them to this. In this place, the teacher will have to convey theoretical knowledge to the students using his own effective work

methods. For example, the music of a song sung in class or a work listened to has a certain feeling and character, artistic-ideal content (thematics, images, author's opinion) and their unique combination in the character of the melody (joyfulness, cheerfulness, solemnity, playfulness, melancholy, etc.), as well as understanding and explaining the direction of movement of the melody (down to top) is the first prelude to success on this path. After achieving such qualifications, they move on to more complex tasks, i.e., to the next stage. In this place, attention is paid to information about the composition of melody sounds, their long and short, and how they are expressed in notation. In this case, giving a description of the melody, showing it in examples (depending on the direction of movement in the sheet music, its writing on a poster or blackboard) gives a good result. Playing notes from a piece of music on clappers and children's instruments, rhythmically accompanying the music, performing movements that match the music (ie dance elements, feeling the way, stepping and hokozos) students feel good and has a positive effect on the imagination of theoretical knowledge.

In conclusion, the use of our historical heritage in the teaching of pedagogy is of great importance for students to acquire comprehensive knowledge, to increase the professional knowledge and skills of future specialists, and to form the skills of applying theoretical knowledge to practice. Forming the general, including musical worldviews of students, is an important task for the musical culture of secondary schools, as well as the cultivation of practical performance skills in them. Achieving this goal requires a music teacher to work tirelessly on himself, to have a broad outlook on musical and secular knowledge, and to have high performance skills. In addition, in order to fully convey the knowledge and skills that the teacher has to the students, he must have a high level of pedagogical skills, correctly choose the methods, methods and technologies used in the lesson, and from these methods and technologies need to be used effectively.

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